

UYURMA TENGLAMASI UCHUN MANBA HADINI TIKLASH MASALASI.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Uyurma tenglamasi uchun manba hadini tiklash masalasi bayon qilingan.

Kalit so'zlar: Bir o'lchamli uyurma-tok tenglamasi, boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shart, manba hadi, Identifikatsiya masalasi, teskari masala, oshkormas ayirmali sxema, progonka metodi, turg'unlik sharti, to'r funksiyasi

Masalaning qo'yilishi

Bir o'lchamli uyurma-tok tenglamasi quyidagicha ko'rinishga ega:

$$\frac{\partial \omega}{\partial t} + \psi \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x} = v \frac{\partial^2 \omega}{\partial x^2} + Q(t, x), \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < t < T, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = -\omega, \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < t \leq T. \quad (2)$$

Tenglamalar $\psi_0^{j+1} = \xi_1 \psi_1^{j+1} + \eta_1 = 0$ va (2) quyidagi boshlang'ich va chegaraviy shartlar bilan qaraladi:

$$\psi(0, x) = 0, \quad \omega(0, x) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\psi(t, 0) = \psi(t, 1) = 0, \quad \frac{\partial \psi(t, 0)}{\partial x} = 0, \quad (4)$$

$$\omega(t, 0) = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi(t, 0)}{\partial x^2}, \quad \omega(t, 1) = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi(t, 1)}{\partial x^2}. \quad (5)$$

To'g'ri masala (1)-(5) ko'rinishida qo'yiladi.

Tenglama (1) ning ma'lum funksiyalari $\omega(x, t)$, $\psi(x, t)$ orqali manba hadi $Q(t, x)$ ni aniqlash talab etiladigan teskari masalasini qaraymiz. Funksiya $Q(t, x)$

$$Q(t, x) = Q_0 \eta(t) \varphi(x), \quad (6)$$

ko'rinishida berilgan deb hisoblaymiz. Bunda ifoda (6) dagi funksiya $\varphi(x)$ berilgan deb, manbaning vaqtdan bog'liqligi - funksiya $\eta(t)$ esa noma'lum hisoblanadi. Ushbu bog'liqlik funksiya $\omega(x, t)$ ni ba'zi ichki nuqtalar $0 < x^* < 1$ da qo'shimcha kuzatish orqali tiklanadi :

$$\omega(x^*, t) = z(t). \quad (7)$$

Uyurma tenglamasining o'ng tomonini aniqlash masalasi (1)-(7) ga keldik.

Identifikatsiya masalasini yechish quyidagi cheklovlar ostida ko'rib chiqiladi:

1. $\varphi(x^*) \neq 0$,
2. $\varphi(x)$ - yetarli silliq funksiya ($\varphi \in C^2[0,1]$),
3. hisoblash sohasi chegarasida $\varphi(x) = 0$.

Teskari masala yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda izlanadi :

$$\omega(t, x) = \theta(t)\varphi(x) + w(t, x), \quad (8)$$

bu yerda

$$\theta(t) = \int_0^t \eta(s) ds. \quad (9)$$

Ifoda (8), (9) larni (1), (2), (6) ifodalarga qo'yish $w(x, t)$ uchun quyidagi tenglamalarni beradi:

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \psi \left[\theta(t) \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right] = v \left[\theta(t) \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \right], \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < t \leq T, \quad (10)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = -[\theta(t)\varphi(x) + w(t, x)], \quad 0 < x < 1, \quad 0 < t \leq T. \quad (11)$$

Ifoda (8) ni shart (7) ga qo'yib hisoblash noma'lum $\theta(t)$ uchun quyidagi ifodaga olib keladi:

$$\theta(t) = \frac{1}{\varphi(x^*)} [z(t) - w(t, x^*)]. \quad (12)$$

Ifoda (12) ni ifoda (10) va (11) larga qo'yish izlanayotgan yuklangan tenglamalarni beradi

$$\frac{\partial w}{\partial t} + \psi \frac{\partial w}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{\varphi(x^*)} [z(t) - w(t, x^*)] \left[\psi \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} - v \frac{\partial^2 \varphi}{\partial x^2} \right] = v \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2}, \quad (13)$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial x^2} = -\frac{1}{\varphi(x^*)} [z(t) - w(t, x^*)] \varphi(x) - w(t, x). \quad (14)$$

Tenglama $w(t, x)$ uchun chegaraviy shart quyidagi ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$w(t, 0) = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi(t, 0)}{\partial x^2}, \quad w(t, 1) = -\frac{\partial^2 \psi(t, 1)}{\partial x^2}, \quad (15)$$

$$\psi(t, 0) = 0, \quad \psi(t, 1) = 0, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T. \quad (16)$$

Ifoda (9) dan yordamchi funksiya $\theta(t)$ uchun quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$\theta(0) = 0. \quad (17)$$

Bu boshlang'ich shartni qo'llash imkonini beradi

$$w(0, x) = \omega(0, x) = 0, \quad \psi(0, x) = 0, \quad 0 < x < 1. \quad (18)$$

Shunday qilib teskari masala (1)-(7) manbaning noma'lum vaqtga bog'liqligi uchun ifodalar (9), (12) lar bilan yuklangan tenglama uchun chegaraviy masala (13)-(18) sifatida shakllanadi.

Soha $\bar{D}$ da koordinata x va vaqt t bo'yicha mos ravishda teng oraliqli to'r kiritamiz:

$$\bar{\Omega} = \bar{\Omega}_h \times \Omega_\tau = \left\{ (x_i, t_j), x_i = i \cdot h, t_j = j \cdot \tau, 0 \leq i \leq N, 0 \leq j \leq M, h = 1/N, \tau = T/M \right\}.$$

Soddalik uchun kuzatish nuqtasi $x = x^*$ ichki tugun $i = k$ bilan mos tushadi deb hisoblaymiz.

Tenglamalar sistemasi (13), (14) ni yechish uchun sof oshkormas ayirmali sxemani qo'llaymiz. Tenglamalar (13), (14) ni approksimatsiya qilamiz

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{w_i^{j+1} - w_i^j}{\tau} + \psi_i^j \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^j}{2h} + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left[z^{j+1} - w_k^{j+1} \right] \left[\psi_i^j (\varphi'_x)_i - v (\varphi''_x)_i \right] = \\ = v \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2w_i^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{\psi_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2\psi_i^{j+1} + \psi_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2} = -\frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left[z^{j+1} - w_k^{j+1} \right] \varphi_i - w_i^{j+1}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1. \quad (20)$$

Ayirmali masalaning qo'yilishida chegaraviy shart (15) ni Vuds sharti bilan almashtiramiz. Tenglamalar (15)-(18) ni approksimatsiyalab quyidagiga ega bo'lamiz:

$$w_0^{j+1} + \frac{w_1^{j+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_0^j - \psi_1^j)}{h^2},$$

$$w_N^{j+1} + \frac{w_{N-1}^{j+1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_N^j - \psi_{N-1}^j)}{h^2}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (21)$$

$$\psi_0^{j+1} = 0, \quad \psi_N^{j+1} = 0 \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (22)$$

$$w_i^0 = \omega_i^0 = 0, \quad \psi_i^0 = 0, \quad i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, N. \quad (23)$$

Ayirmali masala (19)-(23) yechimidan ifoda (12) ga muvofiq, ushbu munosabatlarni shart $\theta^0 = 0$ bilan to'ldirib quyidagini aniqlaymiz:

$$\theta^{j+1} = \frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left(z^{j+1} - w_k^{j+1} \right), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (24)$$

Tenglik (9) ni e'tiborga olib, o'ng tomonning izlangan vaqtdan bog'liqligi uchun oddiy sonli differensiallash protsedurasini qo'llaymiz:

$$\eta^{j+1} = \frac{\theta^{j+1} - \theta^j}{\tau}, \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M-1. \quad (25)$$

Ayirmali sxema (19)-(23) ni yechish yangi vaqt qatlamida nostandart (nolokal) bo'lishiga qaramasdan katta muammo emas. Tenglama (19) ichki tugunlarda quyidagicha bo'ladi :

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \frac{w_i^{j+1}}{\tau} + \psi_i^j \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} - \nu \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2w_i^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2} + \\
 & + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left(\nu \varphi_{x,i}'' - \psi_i^j \varphi_{x,i}' \right) w_k^{j+1} = \frac{w_i^j}{\tau} + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} z^{j+1} \left[\nu \varphi_{x,i}'' - \psi_i^j \varphi_{x,i}' \right], \\
 & \frac{w_i^{j+1}}{\tau} + \psi_i^j \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{2h} - \nu \frac{w_{i+1}^{j+1} - 2w_i^{j+1} + w_{i-1}^{j+1}}{h^2} + \\
 & + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left(\nu \varphi_{x,i}'' - \psi_i^j \varphi_{x,i}' \right) w_k^{j+1} = g_i^j, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N-1, \quad j=0,1,\dots,M-1,
 \end{aligned} \tag{26}$$

$$g_i^j = \frac{w_i^j}{\tau} + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} z^{j+1} \left[\nu \varphi_{x,i}'' - \psi_i^j \varphi_{x,i}' \right]$$

bu yerda

Sistema (21), (25) ning yechimi quyidagi ko'rinishda izlanadi:

$$w_i^{j+1} = y_i + w_k^{j+1} u_i, \quad i=0,1,\dots,N. \tag{27}$$

Ifoda (27) ni (26) ga qo'yib yordamchi funksiyalar y_i , u_i uchun to'r masalasini shakllantiramiz

$$\frac{y_i}{\tau} + \psi_i^j \frac{y_{i+1} - y_{i-1}}{2h} - \nu \frac{y_{i+1} - 2y_i + y_{i-1}}{h^2} = g_i^j, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N-1, \tag{28}$$

$$y_0 + \frac{y_1}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_0^j - \psi_1^j)}{h^2}, \quad y_N + \frac{y_{N-1}}{2} = \frac{3(\psi_N^j - \psi_{N-1}^j)}{h^2}, \tag{29}$$

$$\frac{u_i}{\tau} + \psi_i^j \frac{u_{i+1} - u_{i-1}}{2h} - \nu \frac{u_{i+1} - 2u_i + u_{i-1}}{h^2} + \frac{1}{\varphi_k} \left(\nu \varphi_{x,i}'' - \psi_i^j \varphi_{x,i}' \right) = 0, \tag{30}$$

$i=1,2,\dots,N-1,$

$$u_0 = 0, \quad u_N = 0. \tag{31}$$

Shundan so'ng ifoda (27) ga ko'ra w_k^{j+1} topiladi:

$$w_k^{j+1} = \frac{y_k}{1 - u_k}. \tag{32}$$

To'r masalalari (28), (29) va (30), (31) standart hisoblanadi.

Tenglama (28), (30) quyidagi ko'rinishga keltiriladi:

$$A_i y_{i-1} - C_i y_i + B_i y_{i+1} = -f_i^j, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N-1, \tag{33}$$

$$A_i u_{i-1} - C_i u_i + B_i u_{i+1} = -\bar{f}_i^j, \quad i=1,2,\dots,N-1, \tag{34}$$

bu yerda

$$A_i = \frac{\nu\tau}{h^2} + \frac{\tau}{2h} \psi_i^j, \quad B_i = \frac{\nu\tau}{h^2} - \frac{\tau}{2h} \psi_i^j, \quad C_i = \frac{2\nu\tau}{h^2} + 1,$$

$$f_i^j = w_i^j + \frac{\tau}{\varphi_k} z^{j+1} \left[v\varphi''_{x,i} - \psi_i^j \varphi'_{x,i} \right], \quad \bar{f}_i^j = -\frac{\tau}{\varphi_k} \left(v\varphi''_{x,i} - \psi_i^j \varphi'_{x,i} \right).$$

Sistemalar (33) va (34) lar uchun progonka metodining turg'unlik sharti

$$|C_i| \geq |A_i| + |B_i| \quad \text{bajariladi.}$$

Chegaraviy masalalar (29), (33) larni progonka metodi bilan yechish algoritmi ushbu ko'rinishda bo'ladi:

$$y_i = \alpha_{i+1} y_{i+1} + \beta_{i+1}, \quad i = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (35)$$

$$\alpha_{i+1} = \frac{B_i}{C_i - A_i \alpha_i}, \quad \beta_{i+1} = \frac{A_i \beta_i + f_i^j}{C_i - A_i \alpha_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (36)$$

$$y_0 = \alpha_1 y_1 + \beta_1, \quad y_0 = -0.5 y_1 + 3 \left(\psi_0^j - \psi_1^j \right) / h^2, \\ \alpha_1 = -0.5, \quad \beta_1 = 3 \left(\psi_0^j - \psi_1^j \right) / h^2, \quad (37)$$

$$y_{N-1} = \alpha_N y_N + \beta_N, \quad (38)$$

$$y_N + \frac{y_{N-1}}{2} = 3 \left(\psi_N^j - \psi_{N-1}^j \right) / h^2, \quad (39)$$

Ifoda (38) ni (39) ga qo'yib y_N uchun quyidagi ifodaga ega bo'lamiz

$$y_N = \left[3 \left(\psi_N^j - \psi_{N-1}^j \right) / h^2 - 0.5 \beta_N \right] / (1 + 0.5 \alpha_N), \quad (40)$$

Endi chegaraviy masalalar (31), (34) ni progonka metodi bilan yechish uchun quyidagi formulalarga ega bo'lamiz

$$\bar{u}_i = \bar{\alpha}_{i+1} \bar{u}_{i+1} + \bar{\beta}_{i+1}, \quad i = N-1, N-2, \dots, 1, 0, \quad (41)$$

$$\bar{\alpha}_{i+1} = \frac{B_i}{C_i - A_i \bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad \bar{\beta}_{i+1} = \frac{A_i \bar{\beta}_i + \bar{f}_i^j}{C_i - A_i \bar{\alpha}_i}, \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, N-1, \quad (42)$$

$$\bar{u}_0 = \bar{\alpha}_1 \bar{u}_1 + \bar{\beta}_1, \quad \bar{u}_0 = 0, \quad \bar{\alpha}_1 = 0, \quad \bar{\beta}_1 = 0, \quad (43)$$

$$\bar{u}_N = 0. \quad (44)$$

Bu yerda teskari masala modeli

$$\psi_0^{j+1} = \xi_1 \psi_1^{j+1} + \eta_1 = 0 \quad \text{va} \quad Q(t, x) = Q_0 \eta(t) \varphi(x),$$

uchun hisoblash natijalarini keltiramiz. Qaralayotgan to'g'ri masala (1)-(5) ni ba'zi berilgan o'ng tomoni bilan sonli eksperiment o'tkazamiz. O'ng tomon quyidagi bog'liqliklar bilan beriladi:

$$\varphi(x) = \sin \pi x, \quad 0 \leq x \leq 1,$$

$$\eta(t) = t^2 + 1, \quad 0 \leq t \leq T = 0.4,$$

$$Q_0 = 100.$$

Masala $M = 400$, $N = 21$ bo'lgan to'rda sonli yechiladi.

Quyida $x^* = 0.5$ nuqtada kuzatish bo'yicha o'ng tomonni tiklash natijalari keltirilgan.

Hisoblash natijalari bo'yicha to'r funksiyasi z^j beriladi.

Teskari masalani yechishda to'r funksiyasi $\varphi(t)$ tasodifiy xatoliklar bilan buziladi.

Funksiya z_δ^j quyidagicha bo'lsin:

$$z_\delta^j = z^j + 2\delta \left(\sigma^j - \frac{1}{2} \right), \quad j = 0, 1, \dots, M,$$

bu yerda σ^j - interval $[0, 1]$ da teng oraliqli taqsimlangan tasodifiy funksiya. Kattalik δ esa xatolik darajasi.

1-rasmda $\delta = 0.0025$ xatolik darajasida z_δ va z funksiyalar tasvirlangan.

1-rasm. Aniq va qo'zg'atilgan dastlabki ma'lumotlar: z va z_δ .

Aniq va uyurma tenglamasining vaqtdan bog'liq bo'lgan o'ng qismining tiklangan yechimi rasm 1 da tasvirlangan, rasm 2 da masalaning $\delta = 0.0025$, rasm 3 da masalaning $\delta = 0.001$, rasm 4 da masalaning $\delta = 0.0005$ dagi aniq va taqribiy yechimlari berilgan. Xatolik darajasi kichraytirilgan sari yechim yanada aniqroq tiklanadi.

2-rasm. Aniq va taqribiy yechimning $\delta = 0,0025$ dagi ko'rinishi.

3-rasm . Aniq va taqribiy yechimning $\delta = 0,001$ dagi ko'rinishi.

4-rasm. Aniq va taqribiy yechimning $\delta = 0,0005$ dagi ko'rinishi.

Qaralayotgan uyurma tenglamasi uchun teskari masalani yechish hisoblash algoritmi boshqa umumiyroq masalalarni yechishda ham qo'llanishi mumkin.

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